

THE PROCESSING AND IMPROVEMENT OF HEMP FIBRE REINFORCED BIOCOMPOSITE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY: Hemp fibre reinforced thermoplastic composite materials are strong, stiff, lightweight and recyclable, but possess mechanical properties well below their potential values. The aim of this research was to produce an improved hemp fibre reinforced polypropylene composite material, and to determine the effects of various fabrication variables on composite mechanical properties. An investigation was conducted to determine a suitable alkali fibre treatment method to separate fibres from their fibre bundles, to remove fibre cementing materials, and to retain fibre strength. An alkali treatment involving the digestion of fibres in a 10% wt NaOH solution at a maximum processing temperature of 160⁰C and a hold time of 45 minutes was found to produce strong fibres with good fibre separation. Alkali treated fibres, polypropylene and a maleic anhydride modified polypropylene (MAPP) coupling agent were compounded in a twin-screw extruder, and injection moulded into composite tensile test specimens. The strongest composite consisted of polypropylene with 40% wt NZ hemp fibre and 3%wt MAPP, and had a tensile strength of 47MPa. The effects of fibre content, MAPP content, fibre length and fibre treatment on the tensile strength and Young's modulus of composites were also investigated.

KEYWORDS: Hemp Fibre, Polypropylene, Interfacial Bonding, Extrusion, Injection Moulding.

INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced composite materials have been widely accepted as the materials of choice for many structural and non-structural applications in the aerospace, boat-building and automotive industries. The most commonly used composite reinforcements are glass, carbon, boron and aramid fibres, which result in composite materials with high stiffness to weight and high strength to weight ratios when compared to conventional materials. However, advanced composite materials containing carbon and aramid fibres are prohibitively expensive for use in low-cost consumer goods. Furthermore, cheaper synthetic fibres such as E-glass can be harmful to those working with them, and they are abrasive and cause excessive wear on processing machinery. The main problem with glass and other synthetic fibre composites is that they are difficult to dispose of at the end of their lifetimes. The fibres cannot be incinerated as the residues cause furnace damage, and they cannot be recycled. The only method of disposal is to discard the waste in landfills, which is becoming more costly in many countries due to the implementation of landfill taxes.

Natural fibres, including industrial hemp, are becoming increasingly popular alternatives to glass fibre and have the potential to be used in cheaper, more sustainable and more environmentally friendly composite materials. Industrial hemp fibres (*Cannabis sativa* L), are cheap, abundant and renewable, and can be produced at low cost in many parts of the developing world. The Young's modulus of hemp fibres can reach that of E-glass, and a lower density means that hemp has a specific strength comparable to E-glass.

Unlike synthetic fibres, natural fibres require very little energy to produce, and because they possess high calorific values, can be incinerated at the end of their lifetime for energy recovery [1]. All plant-derived fibres utilise carbon dioxide when they are grown, and can therefore be considered CO₂ neutral as they can be burned at the end of their lifetime with no additional CO₂ being released into the atmosphere. Glass fibres, on the other hand, are not CO₂ neutral and require substantial burning of fossil fuels to provide the energy needed for production. The burning of fossil fuel based products releases enormous amounts of CO₂ into the atmosphere, and this phenomenon is believed to be the main cause of the greenhouse effect and the world's climatic changes [2].

Natural fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites, unlike their glass counterparts, do not splinter during fracture, therefore making them suitable for crash-absorbing applications where safety is of concern. One of the most distinct advantages of using natural fibres in reinforced thermoplastic composites is the fact that the fibres are incredibly durable, and can be recycled several times with little reduction in strength and stiffness [3]. Synthetic fibres on the other hand, tend to fracture with further processing and recycling, resulting in significant fibre length reductions [4].

The potential for natural fibres to be used in recyclable composite materials has sparked widespread interest in many industries. Recent European government regulations are encouraging the development and use of natural fibres in the automotive industry. In July 2002, The European Union Council of Ministers approved the EU end-of-life vehicle directive, which will have a huge impact on the materials and processing methods used to produce motor vehicles in the future. The directive states that from 2015 onwards, all new vehicles should be 85% reusable and recyclable by weight, 10% can be used for energy recovery and only 5% can be disposed of in landfills [5].

The potential applications for natural fibre composites are endless, and it could be possible to engineer such composites specifically for applications such as motor vehicle interiors, furniture, sports equipment and packaging.

Unfortunately, the current generation of natural fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites do not offer sufficient mechanical properties to warrant their use in more demanding structural and load bearing applications. Natural fibres are polar in nature, which can lead to poor fibre-matrix interfacial bonding, and subsequently reduced mechanical properties when used in non-polar thermoplastic matrices. It is therefore necessary to modify the fibres, the matrix or both to produce a composite with improved mechanical properties. A coupling agent such as maleic anhydride modified polypropylene (MAPP) considerably improves the wettability and adhesion of cellulose fibres with polypropylene, resulting in increases in composite tensile strength and Young's modulus [6]. MAPP acts as a bridge between the non-polar polypropylene matrix and the polar fibres by chemically bonding with available fibre hydroxyl groups (OH groups), and bonding to the matrix by means of chain entanglement. Other coupling agents have also been investigated, but MAPP still remains one of the most popular coupling agents that have been tested in the production and research of natural fibre composites [7].

Alkali fibre treatments have also been found to improve the strength of natural fibre composites. A strong NaOH treatment has been successfully used to remove lignin, hemicelluloses and other alkali soluble compounds from the surface of the fibre, thus increasing the number of reactive OH groups on the fibre surface available for chemical bonding [8]. Alkali treatments also have the effect of separating the individual fibres from their fibre bundles, as well as roughening up the fibre surface to aid mechanical interlocking between the fibre and matrix [9].

The purpose of this research was to improve the mechanical properties of hemp fibre reinforced polypropylene composites by: (a) improving the fibre quality by performing and comparing different NaOH fibre treatments, (b) utilising a MAPP coupling agent to improve the fibre-matrix interfacial bonding within the composites, (c) using optimally alkali treated fibres in composites, and (d) varying fibre length in composites.

The effects of various fabrication variables on the composite mechanical properties were also determined.

MATERIALS

Two sources of industrial hemp (*Cannabis sativa* L.) were used in this investigation, namely: (1) semi-retted hemp stalks grown in the Hawkes Bay region of New Zealand (NZ hemp); and (2) retted hemp bast fibre grown in the United Kingdom (UK hemp), supplied by Hemcore(UK). Polypropylene (Icorene™ PP CO14RM) was used as the composite matrix; and A-C 950P high molecular weight MAPP, supplied by Honeywell International Inc, USA, was used as the coupling agent.

EXPERIMENTAL

Hemp Fibre Treatments

NZ hemp was scutched to remove the bast fibre from the woody core, after which the bast fibre tissue was chopped into lengths of approximately 10cm. Small quantities of fibre were then weighed and placed in 1 litre stainless steel canisters with a pre-mixed NaOH solution, such that the fibre:liquor ratio was 1:6 by weight. The canisters were then inserted into a small lab-scale pulp digester for alkali treatment. The following treatment variables were manipulated for the different alkali treatments:

- (1) NaOH concentration: 10% or 15% NaOH solutions (by weight),
- (2) Processing temperature: 160⁰C or 180⁰C,
- (3) Hold time at the maximum temperature: 15 minutes or 45 minutes.

After treatment, the fibres were thoroughly washed for 10 minutes using a pulp and paper fibre-washer. Fibres were then dried at 80⁰C for 48 hours.

UK hemp fibre was alkali treated only with a 10% NaOH solution, at a maximum processing temperature of 160⁰C and a hold time of 45 minutes.

Single Fibre Tensile Testing

Single hemp fibres were tensile tested according to the ASTM D3379-75 Standard Test Method for Tensile Strength and Young's Modulus for High-Modulus Single Filament Materials. Fibres (treated and untreated) were separated by hand, and then mounted on cardboard mounting-cards with 10mm holes punched into them (ie 10mm gauge length). A small amount of PVA glue was applied to the two edges on either side of the hole along the length of the card, and the fibres were carefully put into place. The fibres were then inspected, under an optical microscope with a calibrated eyepiece at 200x magnification, to determine the average diameter of each fibre, and to ensure that only one fibre was present on each card. The mounted fibres were then placed in the grips of an Instron-4204 tensile testing machine, and the supporting sides of the mounting cards were carefully cut using a hot-wire cutter. The fibres were then tensile tested to failure at a rate of 0.5mm/min using a 10N-load cell. Average strengths were obtained using results from thirty specimens.

Composite Extrusion and Injection Moulding

Alkali treated and untreated fibres were chopped into lengths of 1-3mm (short fibres) using an industrial granulator, or manually chopped into ± 10 mm lengths (long fibres) using a guillotine, and then dried at 80⁰C for 48 hours. The chopped hemp fibres, polypropylene and a maleic anhydride modified polypropylene coupling agent (MAPP) were compounded in a ThermoPrism TSE-16-TC twin-screw extruder, such that composites with varying weight fractions of fibre, MAPP and polypropylene were produced.

The extruded composites were then granulated in an industrial granulator to produce composite pellets suitable for injection moulding. Composites reinforced with long fibres were granulated to pellet sizes of between 3 and 6mm in length, while the short fibre composites were granulated to pellet sizes of between 1mm to 4mm in length. The composite pellets were then dried at 80⁰C for 48 hours before being injection moulded into Type 1 tensile test specimens (as specified by the ASTM D638-01 standard) using a BOY15-S injection-moulding machine.

Composite Tensile Testing

Tensile test specimens were placed in a conditioning chamber at 23⁰C \pm 3⁰C and 50% \pm 5% relative humidity for 40 hours. The specimens were then tested using an Instron-4204 tensile testing machine fitted with a 5kN-load cell, and operating at a rate of 5mm/min. An Instron 2630-112 extensometer was used to measure the strain. The composite specimens were tested to failure, whereas the non-fibre containing specimens were only tested to the point of maximum stress due to excessive necking. Ten specimens were used for each test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Effect of Alkali Treatment on Single Fibre Tensile Strength

From the results in Table 1, it can be seen that each of the three alkali treatment variables had an effect on the tensile strength of the treated NZ hemp fibres. Treatments 1, 2 and 4 produced fibres that were stronger than the untreated fibres, whereas treatments 3, 5 and 6 resulted in weaker fibres.

Table 1: Effect of fibre treatment on the tensile strength (σ_{max}) of single hemp fibres

Hemp fibre origin	Treatment no.	NaOH concentration	Max process temp (°C)	Hold time (min)	σ_{max} (MPa)	Std Dev
NZ	1	10%	160	15	664	208
NZ	2	10%	160	45	677	187
NZ	3	10%	180	15	449	121
NZ	4	15%	160	15	632	185
NZ	5	15%	160	45	532	137
NZ	6	15%	180	15	280	101
NZ	Untreated	-	-	-	607	210
UK	2	10%	160	45	347	106
UK	Untreated	-	-	-	514	275

The increase in NZ hemp fibre strength for treatments 1, 2, and 4 can be attributed to the removal of non-cellulosic fibre components that are weaker than the cellulose, or to an increase in the cellulose crystallinity as a result of the alkali treatment. The increase in the crystallinity index percentage of alkali-treated fibres occurs because of the removal of the cementing materials (ie lignin, pectin and hemicellulose), which leads to better packing of the cellulose chains. In addition, alkali treatment leads to a decrease in the spiral angle and an increase in the molecular orientation of the cellulose chains [10]. The decrease in strength for treatments 3, 5 and 6 can be attributed to the degradation of cellulose at temperatures above 160°C [11] and at high NaOH concentrations. For the semi-retted NZ hemp fibre, treatment no.2 appeared to produce the strongest fibres. These fibres also appeared to be relatively well separated from their fibre bundles.

The untreated UK hemp fibres appeared to be weaker than the untreated NZ fibres. This could have been due to differences in hemp plant variety, differences in growing conditions and harvest time, or over-retting of the fibres. Retting is a commonly used method to separate bast fibre from the woody core material present in a hemp stalk, and involves the controlled bacterial and fungal degradation of the plant stem in an aqueous environment. Retting does not reduce fibre strength, but over-retting may result in some cellulose degradation and subsequent fibre strength reductions.

The alkali treated UK hemp fibres appeared to be considerably weaker than the untreated UK hemp fibres. Unlike the semi-retted NZ hemp, the UK hemp had been fully retted, thus removing greater amounts of the cementing materials holding the individual fibres together. The absence of these cementing materials to react with the NaOH during alkali treatment may have resulted in the NaOH degrading the cellulose to a greater extent than if the cementing materials were present. It can therefore be seen that the optimum treatment conditions for one source of hemp fibre may not be the optimum conditions for another.

Effect of Hemp Fibre and MAPP Content on the Tensile Strength and Young's Modulus of Composites

A range of composites were produced with different fibre and MAPP contents. Composites were made with NZ hemp fibres that had previously been alkali treated using treatment no.2. Fibres and extruded composites were chopped using an industrial granulator to produce short fibres and short fibre composites.

From the results in Fig.1, it can be seen that composite tensile strengths increased with increases in the hemp fibre and MAPP contents. The tensile strength increased up to a fibre content of 40%wt, and then decreased thereafter. Composites containing 50%wt hemp were extremely difficult to extrude and injection mould, and the reduced polymer content resulted in poor “wetting out” of fibres with the polymer matrix. The increase in fibre content also resulted in reduced fibre dispersion within the composite test specimens.

The alkali treated NZ hemp fibres used had a tensile strength of 677 MPa, compared to 23 MPa for the polypropylene matrix, so it was expected that increases in the fibre content would have considerably increased the composite strength. However, due to inefficient adhesion between the fibres and matrix, the tensile strengths of the uncoupled composites were well below their potential values. By adding 3%wt MAPP, the fibre-matrix interfacial bond strength was greatly improved, and a tensile strength of 47 MPa was achieved for composites with a fibre content of 40%wt. It was also noted that no significant increases in strength were observed for un-reinforced polypropylene with a 3%wt MAPP content.

The results in Fig.2 show that an increase in fibre content greatly improved the Young’s modulus of the composites, whilst an increase in MAPP content only slightly improved the Young’s modulus values. The relationship between fibre content and Young’s modulus appears almost linear. It can be seen that the stiffest composite contained 50%wt fibre and 3%wt MAPP, and had a Young’s modulus of 6.76 GPa.

Fig. 1: Effect of fibre and MAPP content on the tensile strength of composites reinforced with short NZ hemp fibre

Fig. 2: Effect of fibre and MAPP content on the Young’s modulus of composites reinforced with short NZ hemp fibre

Effect of Fibre Treatment and MAPP Content on the Tensile Strength and Young’s Modulus of Composites

Composites were produced using untreated UK hemp fibres and UK hemp fibres that had previously been alkali treated using treatment no.2. Fibres and extruded composites were chopped using an industrial granulator, and injection moulded to produce short fibre composites with a fibre content of 40%wt.

From the results in Fig.3, it can be seen that an increase in the MAPP content resulted in increases in the tensile strength of composites reinforced with treated and untreated hemp fibre. At MAPP contents of 2%wt and 3%wt, there appeared to be little difference in strength between the treated and untreated fibre composites. MAPP improves the adhesion between fibre and matrix by bonding to available OH groups on the fibre surface, and then by bonding with the matrix through molecular chain entanglement. Not all OH groups are available for

bonding with MAPP, as many are bonded to cementing materials or water. It was thought that at MAPP contents of 2%wt and 3%wt for treated and untreated fibre composites, all the reactive MAPP molecules were bonded to available OH groups on the fibre surface (i.e. there were more OH groups present than MAPP functional groups, thus some of the OH groups remained un-bonded to MAPP).

When the MAPP content was increased from 3%wt to 4%wt for composites containing untreated fibres, there was no significant increase in tensile strength. This was thought to be because the OH groups on these fibres were almost fully saturated at a MAPP content of 3%wt, and few additional OH groups were available for bonding when the MAPP content was increased to 4%wt. On the contrary to untreated fibre composites, composites containing treated fibre and 4%wt MAPP showed a significant increase in tensile strength. Alkali treatments remove non-cellulosic fibre components and cause fibre swelling, resulting in more OH groups on the fibre surface becoming accessible to reactant molecules such as MAPP [12]. It is therefore possible that the alkali treated fibres have a greater number of OH groups available for bonding with MAPP, which results in improved fibre-matrix adhesion and stronger composites when sufficient MAPP is provided [9].

Fig. 3: Effect of fibre treatment and MAPP content on the tensile strength of composites reinforced with short UK hemp fibre

Fig. 4: Effect of fibre treatment and MAPP content on the Young's modulus of composites reinforced with short UK hemp fibre

From the results in Fig.4, an increase in MAPP content did not appear to significantly change the composite Young's modulus for either the treated or untreated fibre composites. It can also be seen that there are large standard deviations in this data, indicating that there were large Young's modulus variations between composite specimens during testing. The error-bars each represent ± 1 standard deviation.

Effect of Fibre Length and MAPP Content on the Tensile Strength and Young's Modulus of Composites

Long and short fibre composites were produced using UK hemp fibres that had previously been alkali treated using treatment no.2. From the results in Fig.5, it can be seen that an increase in fibre length improved the composite strength by 3% for composites containing 2%wt MAPP, and 2.2% for composites containing 3%wt MAPP. It was observed that the long fibre composites did not have good fibre dispersion within the PP matrix compared to their short fibre counterparts. The longer fibres tended to clump together in the centre of the

composite test specimens, resulting in composite strengths that were potentially lower than what they could have been.

It can also be seen in Fig.5 that a considerable increase in composite strength was achieved by increasing the MAPP content from 2wt% to 3wt%.

From the results in Fig.6, it can be seen that an increase in fibre length improved the composite Young's modulus by 20%. An increase in MAPP content had no effect on the composite Young's modulus.

Fig. 5: Effect of fibre length and MAPP content on the tensile strength of composites reinforced with short alkali treated UK hemp fibre

Fig. 6: Effect of fibre length and MAPP content on the Young's modulus of composites reinforced with short alkali treated UK hemp fibre

CONCLUSIONS

In this investigation it was shown that the fibre strength of NZ hemp could be improved by alkali treating the fibres. The optimum alkali treatment involved treating the fibres with a 10% NaOH solution at a maximum processing temperature of 160°C and a maximum temperature hold time of 45 minutes. These optimally treated fibres were well separated and had an average tensile strength of 677 MPa. UK hemp fibres were treated with the same optimum fibre treatment, but appeared to have been significantly weakened during the treatment process. It can therefore be concluded that the optimum treatment conditions for one source of hemp fibre may not be the optimum conditions for another.

Hemp fibre reinforced polypropylene composites were produced using NZ and UK hemp fibre. It was found that the composite tensile strengths increased up to a fibre content of 40%wt, and then decreased thereafter. The composite tensile strengths were also increased with the addition of MAPP, thus improving the fibre-matrix interfacial bonding. The highest composite strengths were achieved with the addition of 4%wt MAPP. Increases in fibre content greatly improved the Young's modulus of composites, whereas increases in MAPP showed very little improvement

It was also found that composites containing 3%wt MAPP and reinforced with alkali treated fibres were stronger than similar composites reinforced with untreated fibres. An increase in fibre length also improved the tensile strength and Young's modulus of composite containing 40%wt fibre.

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